

ANALYSIS OF DOMESTIC TOURIST MARKETS OF BOROBUDUR TEMPLE

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Abstract

This research discusses the market segmentation of domestic tourists in Borobudur Temple. This study is analyses tourist domestic market that brings new perception on how Borobudur become the option to be visited in Yogyakarta. Thus study analyzed the profile of the domestic tourists using quantitative research. Methods of data collection were conducted with questionnaires, field observations, and documentation studies. The results showed that tourists who visited Borobudur Temple mostly came from outside the province (62%) and within the province (38%). When viewed from the provincial origin, then the five largest provinces are domestic tourists from Central Java Province of 38%, while respondents who come from the West Java Province of 13%. Then the respondents from D.I. Yogyakarta with 10%, then East Java Province 9% and DKI Jakarta 9%. Respondents who visited Borobudur Temple were 15-24 years old (36%), male (58%), married (52%), graduated from diploma (46%), still in student status (27%), Revenue per month <Rp. 2,000,000.00 (52%). The majority of respondents have preference type historic sites (52%), preferences for recreational activities (81%), art and culture (53%), friend / family sources (53%), family (52%), had no constraints (43%), day preference on national holidays (39%), in the morning (57%), duration of 1-3 hours (65%), visit frequency 1 times (80%), average / moderate price perception (75%), rate of Borobudur temple at good enough level (58%), and have hope for improvement (45%) location arrangement. Spending at DTW> Rp. 50.000,00 (28%), total expenses during trip <Rp. 200.000,00 (32%), the largest share of expenditure is located on transportation (34%), using land transportation (86%) and air (13%), visiting reason because Borobudur Temple has artistic and cultural value (38%), preference of stay in other hotels / inns (36%), visit planning <1 week earlier (65%), recommend Borobudur Temple (96%), and have a return visit (97%). In comparison of markets within and outside the province, the source of information from friends / family (62%) is preferred by the market within the province. Outside provincial markets (85%) have motivational preferences of visiting for recreation and leisure. The average income of domestic tourists in the province is Rp. 3.138.298 Meanwhile, the average income of tourists outside the province is Rp.3.750.000. Expenditure at Borobudur Temple for respondents in the province is Rp.194.681, - meanwhile for out of province is Rp.202.885.000, Travelers from within the province have an average total of travel expenses of Rp.606.383 and outside the province of Rp.1.264.744. Domestic Tourists in the province have purchasing power of 19% of income per month while from outside have purchasing power of 34% of tourist income per month. For the largest expenditure during the trip is on transportation, tourists

outside the province has a magnitude of 36% and tourists in the province of 32%. For the category recommend, tourists outside the province have 95% and tourists in the province of 98%. The appraisal of tourism facilities is at a sufficiently good level with a value of 3.50, all price aspects considered having a range between 3.25 - 3.46 infrastructure components and promotion is quite good with an average score of 3.55.

Keywords: Borobudur Temple, Market Profile, Segmentation, Domestic Tourist

1. INTRODUCTION

This study is an important part of efforts to establish a more effective cultural tourism marketing strategy and is an effort to understand the characteristics and wants of the market, so it can be an important reference in marketing the products of cultural tourism and in preparing the program promotion. To support the implementation of the analysis in order to obtain optimal results, then conducted direct observation to the research locus. The survey was conducted by questionnaires, interviews and the results were analyzed by quantitative methods, and other supporting data obtained from various sources and references both off-line and on-line.

1.1. Formulation of the problem

Tourism stakeholders tourism area Borobudur temple has not been right in understanding how the profile and what is in the minds of Domestic Travelers, especially the Domestic Tourists who visited the tourist attraction of culture. Therefore, it is necessary to do a deeper understanding of the needs, wishes, and expectations of the Domestic Tourist. From the description, the authors feel the need to conduct research entitled Analysis of Domestic Tourist Market in Borobudur Temple with the formulation of the problem "How is the Profile of Domestic Tourism Market Borobudur Temple?"

1.2. Goals and Benefits

The purpose of this study are (1) To identify the profile of Domestic Tourists at Borobudur Temple which has a prominent cultural tourism attraction in Indonesia. The profile sought includes: (a) Geographic profile; (b) Demographic profile; (c) Psychographic Profile; and (d) Behavioral Profiles, and Market Profiles within and outside the Province; and (2) To identify the assessment of the satisfaction of Domestic Tourists on facilities at Borobudur Temple.

The objectives of this research are (1) The identification of the profile of Domestic Tourists at Borobudur Temple which has a prominent cultural tourism attraction in Indonesia. The purpose of this research is to collect data to obtain the profile of Domestic Tour market in Borobudur Temple comprehensively by considering all related aspects, such as: geography, demography, psychography and behavioral (behavioral) aspects, as well as markets within and outside the province; and (2) The identification of the assessment of Domestic Travelers satisfaction on facilities at Borobudur Temple.

The benefits of this research are for the stakeholders. For the academics to

improve the quality and quantity of research on Borobudur Temple. For the Private (Business) / Party Management: for the development of Borobudur Temple marketing more effective and efficient. For the Government: in order to improve coordination with the manager. And for the Community: in order to improve the quality of comfort and service at Borobudur Temple.

1.3. The scope of research

1.3.1. Scope of Territory

The scope of this research area is in Borobudur Temple, Borobudur District, Central Java Province.

1.3.2. Scope of Material

The scope of this research material in detail as follows:

- a. Identification of Domestic Tour segmentation visiting the tourist area of Borobudur Temple covering 4 dimensions / aspects, namely:
 - 1) Geographical Aspects
 - 2) Demographic Aspects
 - 3) Psychographic Aspects
 - 4) Aspects of Behavior
- b. Analysis of the profile of domestic tourists visiting the tourist area of Borobudur Temple based on the origin of the inner and outer provinces.
- c. Analysis of the assessment of Domestic Travelers satisfaction on the facilities at Borobudur Temple.

1.4. Framework

This research begins with the framework that Domestic Tourists who visit the tourist attraction of culture is still small when compared with natural and artificial tourism attraction. However, one of the cultural tourist attraction visited by many Domestic Tourist is Borobudur Temple. Therefore, the authors feel it is important to analyze the domestic tourists who come to visit Borobudur Temple based on geographical, demographic, psychographic, and behavioral aspects.

In addition to analyzing the segmentation aspect, this study also analyzes the satisfaction of the Domestic Travelers based on the existing facilities, price, infrastructure and promotion that has been done. The results of this study will get the profile of Domestic Tourists coming to Borobudur Temple as well as suggestions that can be given to the development and progress of Borobudur Temple in particular, and for the development and advancement of cultural tourism attraction in general. In order to understand more clearly about this research, we have created a frame of mind in the form of a chart as can be seen in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Frame of Mind

Source: Modification Plog concept (2009) and Middleton (2001)

2. METHOD

The research method used in this research is quantitative research method. This quantitative research using descriptive writing method and tend to use analysis with deductive approach. The deductive approach is an approach that uses logic to draw one or more conclusions based on the given premise. The deductive method of thinking is a method of applying the common things first to be connected in their particular parts. In this research the method used is descriptive method. This method is a method based on problem-solving based on existing facts. The data obtained are explained and then analyzed based on existing theory then drawn the conclusion (Surakhmad, 1985: 140). Descriptive method is used to describe the cultural profile of archipelago tourists. The profile overview covers the demand and supply aspects of the cultural tourism market of the archipelago.

Descriptive method is a study designed to obtain information about the status of a symptom when the study was conducted by survey, ie the study of relatively limited data collection of cases of relatively large numbers. The objective is to collect information on variables based on their scope (Census or sample survey) and the subject (real or unreal).

2.1. Data collection

The data collection tool used as follows:

a. Observation

The types of research undertaken in this technique include observations, and assessment of the condition of the Domestic Tourist market, carried out directly at the location of the Borobudur Temple and is intended to collect the data required by using a data collection tool in the form of checklists (Check list).

b. Distribution of Questionnaires

The distribution of questionnaires conducted to tourists, with a view to know the opinions of each visitor about attractions in the tourist attraction Borobudur Temple, activities, and facilities in the area.

In this study used non probability sampling is a sampling technique that does not provide opportunities / opportunities the same for each element or for members of the population to be selected to be a sample (Sugiyono, 1997: 61). This sampling technique consists of purposive sampling which is sample determination technique for certain purpose only (Sugiyono, 1997: 62) and accidental sampling is sample determination technique based on anyone who by chance meet with researcher and can be used as sample which is assessed as data source (Sugiyono, 1997: 62). The sampling technique used in this research is accidental sampling.

Segmentation is a work based on research that has several steps. Research on market segmentation may use Simple Demographics or Complex Demographic and Multivariate methods. "Segmenting markets is a research-based exercise with several stages. These apply irrespective of whether the method used is simple demographics or complex and multivariate (Kotler, et al, 2005: 414).

2.2. Segmentation Stages

For developing market segments consists of several stages, namely:

1) Quantitative research

Quantitative research should be able to describe the market by using statistical methods to describe each market segment. Usually markets are grouped in 3 or 4 more segments with different approaches. Must have at least 100 respondents using a questionnaire (Kotler, et al, 2005: 414).

2) Analysis

Analyzing the data should be based on the data arrangement used. The most commonly used technique is factor analysis to eliminate correlations of variables, then use cluster analysis to find market segments. There are also techniques of Automatic Interaction Detection (AID) and conjoint analysis (Kotler, et al, 2005: 414). In this study, the

research used the table as a tool to categorize the market.

3) Validation

This stage is the most important stage, because at this stage each segment is created to be accurately analyzed the opportunities contained in each segment (Kotler, et al, 2005: 414).

4) Profiling

After knowing the condition of each segment the last step is to create a profile from the market with the criteria of "distinguishing attitudes, behavior, demographics and so forth" of each segment. Each segment has its own name (Kotler, et al, 2005: 414)

2.3. Population and Sample

The population of this study are Domestic Tourists who visited Borobudur Temple in July 2017. While the sample of this study refers to the opinion of Kotler, et al (2005: 414), that at least must have 100 respondents by using questionnaires, then this study tried to get respondents through questionnaires as much as possible with a minimum limit of 100 respondents with a stratified sampling form (layered sampling).

This form of sampling is included in the probability sampling technique. The layered sampling is a random sampling where the populace is divided into groups called strata. In this study, the strata is divided into two, namely the group of foreign tourists and Domestic Travelers groups. The sampling is only a group of domestic tourists. With the limited time given for approximately 7 days on 10-16 July 2017 (5 days effective in the field), finally got a sample of 125 respondents.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Geographical Aspects

From the geographical aspect data we can know that there are as many as 21 provinces of Domestic Tourist origin who come to visit Borobudur Temple, from Aceh to Papua. This indicates that Borobudur Temple attracts most Domestic Tourist in Indonesia. For the top five Provinces of Domestic Tourist come from Java, Central Java, West Java, D.I. Yogyakarta, DKI Jakarta, and East Java. From the data of province of origin hence can be made marketing strategy which focus on marketing to Domestic Travelers in Java Island which cooperate with travel agency to offer tour package to Borobudur Temple by using land transportation. Here is a table that shows the percentage of visitors to Borobudur Temple from 21 provinces

Table 1: List Percentage of 21 Province

No.	Province of origin	Percentage
1	Aceh	1.60%
2	Sumut	1.60%
3	Riau	0.80%
4	Sumsel	1.60%
5	Lampung	4.00%
6	Kepri	0.80%
7	Jakarta	8.80%
8	Jabar	12.80%
9	Jateng	37.60%
10	Yogyakarta	9.60%
11	Jatim	8.80%
12	Banten	0.80%
13	Bali	1.60%
14	NTB	0.80%
15	Kalbar	1.60%
16	Kalsel	1.60%
17	Kaltim	0.80%
18	Sulut	1.60%
19	Sulteng	0.80%
20	Sultra	0.80%
21	Papua	1.60%

Figure 2. Comparison of the percentage of visitors from inside and outside the province

3.2. Geographical Aspects

From the demographic aspect data we can see that the majority of respondents aged 15-24 years (36%) and 25-34 years (33%) or in youth category Last education Diploma (46%) and SMA (45%) with most of the jobs are students (27%) and employees (22%). The majority of revenue is less than Rp.2.000.000 (52%) and Rp.2.000.000 - Rp.5.000.000 (32%). From the demographic aspect data we can create marketing strategies that focus on teenagers and youth who are mostly students and employees. The management of Borobudur Temple can conduct roadshows and cooperation with schools / colleges and companies to create tour packages to Borobudur Temple. The majority of visitors came from the age range of 15-24 as many as 36%. The majority of visitors from this age range because most come with the romance of a school or college in the context of a study tour,

3.3. Psychographic Aspects

From Psychographic aspect data we can create marketing strategy that focus through the power of word of mouth to mouth promotion and online media. So for the promotion of word of mouth visitors run effectively, then the manager must be able to provide services that exceed the expectations of visitors (beyond the expaction) or commonly known as excellent service. In addition, other strategies can be made or displayed more variety of attractions on a special national holiday since the early morning so that Domestic Tourists who come can spend more time adri 3 hours and spend more money in Borobudur Temple. Program discount can be made for Domestic Tourist who have visited Borobudur Temple Area for the 2nd, 3rd visit and so on, for more Domestic Tour repeaters.

3.4. Behavior Aspects

From the data aspects of behavior we can know that the spending of Domestic Travelers is still relatively small both the expenditure in the area of Borobudur Temple and the total expenditure during the trip.

Especially for the area of Borobudur temple, the standard of food and beverage prices is not too much different from those outside the area. Besides the quality of souvenirs / souvenirs are also improved and the price is adjusted to the quality.

3.5. Market Profile of Origin In and Out of the Province

To facilitate the overall viewing of the market profile within and outside the province and analyze it, the researchers recap the first and second largest percentage of data in table form below.

Table 2. The Largest Percentage of I and II Market Profile In and Out of the Province

No.	Dimensions	Origin	
		In the Province	Outside the Province
1.	Sources of Information	Friends / family (62%) & Online media (21%)	Friends / family (47%) & Online media (22%), Electronic media (22%)
2.	Visiting Motivation	Recreational / leisure motivation (74%) & Study / research (11%)	Recreation / leisure (85%) & Study / research (10%)
3.	Revenue per Month	<Rp.2.000.000 (60%) & Rp.2.000.000 – Rp.5.000.000 (30%)	<Rp.2.000.000 (47%) & Rp.2.000.000 – Rp.5.000.000 (33%)
4.	Spending at Location	<Rp.50.000 (34%) & Rp.101.000 – Rp.200.000 (26%)	<Rp.50.000 (24%) & Rp.101.000 – Rp.200.000 (27%)
5.	Total travel expenses	<Rp.200.000 (45%) & Rp.201.000 – Rp.500.000 (28%)	<Rp.200.000 (24%) & Rp.201.000 – Rp.500.000 (27%)
6.	Average income per month	Rp.3.138.298	Rp.3.750.000
7.	Average Total Spending on Trips	Rp.606.383	Rp.1.264.744
8.	<i>Purchasing Power</i>	19%	34%
9.	Largest Spending	Transportation (32%) & Souvenir (26%)	Transportation (36%) & Accommodation (29%)
10.	Recommend	Yes (98%)	Yes (95%)

From the market profile data in and outside the province we can know that purchasing power market from outside the province is greater than within the province. Therefore, the promotion can be focused on markets outside the province because it proves to provide more income to the Tourism Area of Borobudur Temple.

3.6. Assessment of Satisfaction of Wisnus

Wisnus's satisfaction analysis of DTW facilities discusses several variables related to DTW, namely worship conditions, toilets / toilets, information services, security, health and trade, as can be seen in table below.

Table 3. Assessment of Borobudur Temple Facility

No.	Criteria	Assessment
1	Condition of Borobudur Temple	3.83
2	Information Service Facility	3.69
3	Worship Facilities	3.64
4	Security Service Facilities	3.59
5	Health Service Facilities	3.45
6	Diversity of Attractions	3.42
7	Souvenir and Culinary Center	3.33
8	Toilet Facilities	3.30
9	Parking Facilities	3.26
Average		3.50

In Table 2 it can be seen that the highest value is in Borobudur temple component condition with a value of 3.83 followed by the information service facility component of 3.69. For the third place, there is a component of worship facility with a value of 3.64. In addition, the fourth that still has above average value is the facility of security services. The overall assessment of the components of the Borobudur Temple is getting an average value of 3.50, which means that overall components of Borobudur Temple facilities that are analyzed to get the value of moderate (enough).

Meanwhile, five criteria need to get serious attention because it has a value below the average value. The first criteria to be addressed were health facilities (3.45), both diversity of attractions (3.42), the third criterion was souvenir and culinary center (3.33), followed by toilet / MCK (3.30), and the lowest is the parking facility (3,26).

The five criteria that have value below the average value of satisfaction should be a concern for the manager of Borobudur Temple to be able to improve the quality of facilities. For the components that have been, felt good then continue to be maintained and for components that are not considered good assessment can be increased again for the achievement of the satisfaction of tourists when visiting back to the Borobudur Temple in the future.

Figure 3. Price Components

From Figure 1 it can be seen that the highest value is in the transport price component to the tourist attraction (3.46) followed by the accommodation price component (3.36). For the third order, there is an admission price component (3.34). The overall valuation of the price component at the Borobudur Temple gets an average value of 3.34, which means that the overall component of the price at the Borobudur temple analyzed has a moderate value.

In addition to the two lowest values that have a value below the average that is at the component of the price of souvenir (3.28), and the lowest is on the components of the price of eating and drinking (3.25). For the price of the souvenir must be adjusted to the existing quality. The more good quality the higher the price, but if the quality is less, then it is reasonable if the price is also lower. As for the price of food and drink should be the prices are not much different from the prices of eating and drinking outside Borobudur Temple.

Table 4. Infrastructure and Promotion Assessment

No.	Criteria	Assessment
1	Publication of Tourist Attraction Information	3.82
2	The Availability of Directions to Toward Attraction	3.66
3	Level Hygiene Attraction	3.58
4	Road Conditions	3.55
5	Level of Smoothness of Traffic Towards Borobudur Temple	3.42
Rata-rata		3.55

In Table 3 on the assessment of Infrastructure and Promotion it can be seen that the highest value is in the publication component of tourist attraction information (3.82) followed by the availability component of the direction to the tourist attraction (3.66). For the third rank, there is a component of tourist attraction hyperlevel (3.58), and the fourth is in the road condition component (3.55). The overall assessment of the Infrastructure component and the promotion of Borobudur Temple earned an average value of 3.55, which means that the overall components of Infrastructure and promotion of Borobudur temple analyzed get a moderate value.

Meanwhile, for the lowest value that is below the average value that is on the level of smooth traffic to the tourist attraction (3.42). Therefore, the manager of Borobudur Temple should consider the level of traffic smoothness to Borobudur Temple in cooperation with relevant authorities in regulating highway traffic such as the transportation agency and the police.

4. CONCLUSION

According to data accumulatively in 2016 at Borobudur temple recorded the number of trips amounted to 362,125 wisnus, an increase of 9% from 2015. Meanwhile, the number of trips wisnus who visited Borobudur temple in the first half of 2017 (January - June 2017), recorded the number of visits of 1.269.867 decreased 24% from the first half in 2016. The market profile is one of the keys to the success of a sustainable tourist attraction and has a positive economic impact on the community. In addition, the accuracy of the data regarding the market profile is also as a support to provide the right strategy. Here is the profile of the Domestic Tourist market visiting Borobudur Temple, Central Java.

Viewed from the aspect of the respondent's origin, tourists who visited Borobudur Temple mostly came from outside the province (62%) and within the province (38%). When viewed from the provincial origin, then the five largest provinces are Domestic Tourist from Central Java Province of 38%, while respondents who come from West Java Province of 13%. Then the respondents from D.I. Yogyakarta with 10%, then East Java Province 9 and DKI Jakarta 9%. When identified from the demographic aspect, respondents who visited Borobudur Temple were 15-24 years old (36%), male (58%), married (52%), graduated diploma / degree (46%), still in status students (27%), Revenue per month <Rp. 2,000,000.00 (52%). When viewed from the psychographic aspect, the majority of respondents have preference types of DTW historic sites (52%), preferences for leisure activities (81%), art and culture (53%), friend / family sources (53%) %, family visits (52%), no constraints (43%), day preference on national holidays (39%), in the morning (57%), visit duration 1-3 hours (65%), visit frequency 1 times (39%), do not use tour packages (80%), perception of normal / medium price (75%), rate component of Borobudur temple at good level (58%), and have hope for improvement of location arrangement DTW (45%). In behavioral aspect, spending at DTW > Rp. 50.000,00 (28%), total expenses during trip <Rp. 200.000,00 (32%), the largest share of expenditure is located in transportation (34%), using land transportation (86%) and air (13%), visiting reason because Borobudur Temple has artistic and cultural value (38%), preference of stay in other hotels / inns (36%), visit planning <1 week earlier (65%), recommend Borobudur Temple (96%), and have a return visit (97%).

In comparison of markets within and outside the province, the source of information from friends / family (62%) is preferred by the market within the province. Outside provincial markets (85%) have motivational preferences of visiting for recreation and leisure. The average income of Domestic Travelers in the province is Rp. 3.138.298 Meanwhile, the average income of tourists outside the province is Rp.3.750.000. Expenditure at Borobudur Temple for the respondents in the province is Rp.194.681, - meanwhile for out of province is Rp.202.885.000. Travelers from within the province have an average total of travel expenses of Rp.606.383 and outside the province of Rp.1.264.744. Domestic tourists in the province have purchasing power of 19% of income per month while from outside the province have purchasing power of 34% of tourist income per month. For the largest expenditure during the trip is on transportation, tourists outside the province has a magnitude of 36% and tourists in the province of 32%. For the category recommend, tourists outside the province have 95% and tourists in the province of 98%.

The appraisal of tourism facilities is at a sufficiently good level with a value of 3.50, all aspects of the valued price have a range between 3.25 - 3.46 infrastructure components and promotion is quite good with an average score of 3.55.

Suggestion proposed by researcher in research of analysis of market data of Domestic Tourist at Borobudur Temple is as follows:

Borobudur Temple needs to be packed interesting by looking at the characteristics of the market. In general, every Domestic Tourist spends less than 3 hours, so it takes creative effort to package tourist attractions in Borobudur temple within 3 hours or more. Can also by packing a variety of attractions sequentially each time presentation. Based on field observations by researchers in research data analysis of domestic tourist market is also found on the characteristics of tourist attractions are not coherent, such as the existence of elephant riding. Researchers also propose a package of Domestic Tourist visits from morning until noon with a cheaper price. And with the social media, need to be promoted more Borobudur temple that has the impression "Instagramable".

Development of markets outside the province in the strategy concept is the blue ocean strategy, the development of markets outside the province is a strategy in creating a wider market space. At present, although the market of Borobudur Temple is already dominated by people outside the province, it is still necessary to develop the tourist market outside the province in order to get greater economic impact.

Increased infrastructure is absolutely done by the manager of Borobudur Temple to reach the satisfaction of tourists. Infrastructure development is carried out at least in accordance with the established standards. As pedestrian infrastructure standards refer to the standard PU Permen No. 03 of 2014. Borobudur temple has a zone characteristic where there are areas that require limits on the number of visitors at one time to be maintained and not damaged. Therefore, zoning that is required to adjust the characteristics of the Borobudur Temple area and the determination of the carrying capacity of the tourist area that refers to the physical carrying capacity and the real carrying capacity so that the limits of visit number per day, week, month and year to preserve the cultural values in Borobudur Temple.

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